

EFFECT OF PERSONALITY TYPES ON WORKPLACE HAPPINESS OF UNIVERSITY TEACHERS IN DELHI/NCR

SHILPA BHANDARI

Research Scholar, Department of Management Sciences, Lovely Professional University, Punjab,
Email: Shilpabhandari.92@gmail.com,

Dr. PRETTY BHALLA

Associate Professor, Department of Management Sciences, Lovely Professional University, Punjab,
Email:pretty.21576@lpu.co.in,

Dr. SEEMA GUPTA

Department of Commerce, Deshbandhu College, University of Delhi, Email:seemadelhiuniversity@gmail.com,

SAYEED ZAFAR

University of Business and Technology, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia.
Corresponding Author: Email: sayeed@ugbt.edu.as

Abstract

In universities, teachers are the most important assets who contributes in the holistic growth and development of the system. Teachers are occupied with a bunch of responsibilities including both teaching and administrative task which creates the stress at work. An individual personality plays a significant role in the happiness level. Happier employees are more productive. Organisations across the industry, no doubt try to improve their employee's happiness with the objective to improve their employee's happiness with the objective to achieve higher profitability and company value. The present study aims to investigate the effect of big five traits on workplace happiness of university teachers in Delhi/NCR and to understand how personality can be used as an intervention to foster workplace happiness.

Keywords: Extraversion, Agreeableness, Openness, Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, Happiness, Workplace

Introduction

Workplace happiness is referred to the satisfaction of people with their work. Happiness is generally viewed as an individual's subjective well-being and satisfaction in life. To improve the productivity of employees in the organization, it is important to keep the working environment healthy and happy. Therefore, it is equally important to study the factors that may affect the happiness of employees at work.

How an individual views the idea of happiness may depend upon his/her personality trait. It is generally perceived that a person, who is extrovert, is more likely to be happy as compared to the person who is introvert. Past studies have also suggested that there is a significant relationship of personality with workplace happiness. There are very limited studies in the area

of personality and workplace happiness w.r.t. to teachers. Hence, it is crucial to understand the role of personality traits in the workplace happiness of university teachers.

Recently, various studies have revealed that the personality variables affect the happiness of an individual like extraversion and neuroticism. It has been suggested that the people who are extroverts are happier as compared to people who are neurotic (Pishva et al., 2011).

Happiness is termed as 'Stable Extraversion' (Eysenck, 1983). Happiness of an individual may get affected majorly by four Big- five personality types such as emotional steadiness, extraversion, agreeableness and conscientiousness (DeNeve et al. 1998).

The findings of a parallel study by Yue et al. (2017) revealed that extraversion as a personality variable intermediated an individual women's happiness, whereas, neuroticism intermediated women's depression. (Ziapour, 2018) in his study examine the correlation of personality types with workplace happiness of students. The results revealed the positive correlation between personality and happiness. A similar study was done by (Gyeltshen, 2018), it suggested the workplace happiness as a significant intervention and tool for developing the effectiveness of teachers.

Happier employees are more productive. Organisations across the industry, no doubt try to improve their employee's happiness with the objective to improve their employee's happiness with the objective to achieve higher profitability and company value (**Huang, 2016**). Workplace Happiness has the parameters divided into individual factors (employment risk, meaningfulness of work, job security, relationship with co-workers, recognition and autonomy) and organizational factors (training & development, skill recognition, superior- subordinate relationships, career advancement opportunities). These parameters foster the happiness of employees at workplace. The researchers have captured a detailed glimpse into the mechanisms of workplace happiness and attempted to understand why workplace happiness is so imperious to maintaining motivation of employees **Roy et al. (2020)**. A new method was proposed, tracing happiness/joy and stress via body sign adjustments using "Happimeter" as a smart watch. This smart watch helped in determining an individual's sentiments from the sensor data which was collected using an android wear heart rhythm or movement smart watch. Among 22 workers, the Happimeter was used for three months to assess and evaluate the satisfaction, behaviour and tension of an individual employee at work. The findings of the work stated the applied inferences of such as system for managerial employees. It showed that such sensor-based arrangement can help in predicting the happiness and stress of employees at work. Also, this information can be helpful to foster happiness and satisfaction among employees **Roessler et al. (2020)**. **Chung et al. (2019)** in his research examined the role of personality characters in the happiness of under-graduate students in Malaysia. The data was collected from 131 students using convenience sampling method. It was the first study to investigate the relationship between non-medical student's satisfaction and personality characteristic in Malaysia by using the Oxford happiness scale and NEO-FFI. The results of the study revealed a positive relationship between happiness and the four traits of personality namely, extraversion, conscientiousness, openness, agreeableness. But there is a negative relationship between neuroticism and happiness. The authors have proposed that steps should be taken by

the management of the respective institution to promote student's well-being and satisfaction. The Happiness is a countenance of favourable forms of sentiments, moods, positive attitude and comfort which is of growing importance at workplace. The objective of the research was to explore various literatures to understand the term happiness, its measurement, causes and consequences. The initiative was taken to determine various practices to foster the happiness at work. The data was collected and reviewed from 25 literatures. Author finds a significant relationship between employee's happiness and their efficiency. The organizations are taking initiatives to monitor the attitude and moods of their employees as it affects the success of the business. Therefore, it has been suggested that the organizations should promote happiness and good health among employees **Mohammed (2019)**. The other important aspect of workplace happiness is related to the personality types of employees. It is being stated there is a significant relationship between the five factor personality characters and happiness. The researchers investigated this relationship among the medical sciences students of Kermanshah University, Iran in 2015. The result showed that conscientiousness, extraversion, neuroticism and agreeableness are the best interpreters to measure the happiness. It was also suggested that the type of five factor personality trait that influences happiness the most should be further studies and examined in the form of comparisons among the variables (**Ziapour et al. 2018**). A similar study by **Agbo et al. (2017)** examined the possible mediating role of personality traits on the relationship between the aversion of happiness and the understanding of happiness. Happiness was considered as the incidence of positive and negative effects. The data was collected using self-administered questionnaire of happiness and short of big five inventory scale (Gosling, Rentfrow & Swann, 2003). The findings of the study stated a differed pattern of positive and negative affect due to the mediating role of personality. It was concluded that the higher level of agreeableness and neuroticism potentiated the aversion of happiness on the positive affect whereas; the high level of extraversion, conscientiousness and openness potentiated the weekend influence on happiness. It was suggested to study the personality traits in order to examine their impact on fear of happiness. Besides the role of personality in happiness, various studies also showed the co-worker support as an important determinant of happiness. **Ergun et al. (2017)** concluded that the co-worker support, supervision positively affects the life satisfaction of employees. According to study, each academicians has a different perception towards life satisfaction. Respondents completely agreed to the positive association of co-worker support and life satisfaction while they disagreed to the influence of supervisor support on life satisfaction. Similarly, **Santoso et al. (2016)** examined the relationship between happiness, emotional well-being and stress on the performance of employees in Sri Lanka. The results of the study showed a positive relationship between emotional well-being and performance. The same applied for the association between happiness and respondent's performance but in a lesser degree. The results also stated that there is an obvious negative effect of stress on the performance. The researchers suggested that there should be a longitudinal study wherein, the same respondents should be asked to fill the questionnaire to understand whether and how psychological well-being, happiness and stress of respondent's changes with time with special reference to their socio-economic status. Considering the teacher's happiness in academics, **Abdullah et al. (2016)** studied the relationship between workplace happiness, teacher's self-efficacy, affective commitment and innovative behaviour

among 835 teachers at 167 national secondary schools in Malaysia. The results of the study revealed a direct relationship between workplace happiness and the other three variables. The researchers suggested that the teachers need to increase their level of confidence and trust. The findings of the study could help the management of the schools to foster their work environment in order to enhance teacher's happiness at work. It will also help the teachers to reduce their work load and burden. Another most relevant study was done by **Huang, Hongyi (2016)** examined the role of organization in workplace happiness of project managers in the state of Maryland. The findings revealed that there exists no significant effect of gender, experience or any other demographic aspects on the workplace happiness of professionals. Pleasing work environment, well- managed team and a good working organization are the major factors to promote workplace happiness. **Kirkpatrick (2015)** determined the relationship between personality, happiness and happiness proposed behaviours among employees. The data was collected from university students. The relationship between self-reported extraversion and neuroticism and self-reported affect, HIB engagement was determined. Big five inventory questionnaire was used to determine the personality of an individual student. Study revealed that there is a positive association between extraversion and happiness whereas; there is a substantial negative association between student's happiness and neuroticism. **Wesarat et al. (2015)** examined happiness at individual level. Based on the past studies, the researchers constructed four factors which may affect the happiness of an individual employee: employment status, friendship, work activities and income. The findings of the study revealed that the employed people are happier than the unemployed ones and also voluntary part times employees are happier than those who are the full- time employees. The study also revealed that the income and friendship at work positively affects the happiness of an employee. Though, employees agreed that specific work activities may affect their happiness at work. **Abraham (2015)** conducted a study to find the aspects affecting the happiness of software employees in Bangalore. The study also attempted to examine the relation between employee's job satisfaction and workplace happiness. The findings of the research revealed that their workplace happiness of employees is affected by three main factors namely, organization system, meaning of work and personal resources. Further, workplace happiness plays a vital role in the employee's job satisfaction at their workplace. **Aziz et al. (2014)** endeavoured to study a perceived relation between personality traits and happiness among teachers in Malaysia by investigating their state of subjective well-being. The researcher used big five inventory questionnaire and subjective happiness questionnaire to determine the personality traits and subjective happiness of academicians respectively. The findings revealed that the respondents were in the mid-level of overall happiness which become a key element to enhance the level of their happiness in future. The findings also suggested that the happiness is affected by personality. Extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness and openness has a constructive effect on happiness whereas, neuroticism negatively affect the happiness. **Abedzadeh et al. (2014)** suggested that anxiety and assertiveness have a positive relationship with happiness at work. Mental health of employees increases the happiness and satisfaction of employees. The association between happiness and the components of work life quality of teachers of Illam High School in 2011-12 academic year. Working life components comprised of: payment rate, management support, workplace security, promotion opportunity,

opportunity for professional development and involvement in decision making. The ranking was given to each component of working life quality using multiple regression analysis. Accordingly, workplace security was ranked first, payment rate as second, promotion opportunity as third, involvement in decision making as fourth, management support as fifth and professional development opportunity ranked as sixth. The results showed that teacher's quality of work life was lower than the medium. The finding also revealed that teacher's happiness has appositive relationship with the mechanisms of quality work life except for promotion chance (**Toulabi et al. 2013**). Similarly, **Otken et al. (2013)** studied the importance of work-life balance and its relationship with happiness. The results revealed that work interfering the personal life negatively affects the happiness of an individual. The researchers also suggested to study the contingent factors in order to understand the relationship between work-life balance and happiness at work. **Pishve, Maryan et al. (2011)** stated that extraversion is positively correlated with happiness whereas, neuroticism and psychoticism are negatively correlated with happiness. **Chaiprasit et al. (2011)** concluded the five factors which influences the happiness of employees namely, job inspiration, organizational collective value, relationship, work quality and management. The study revealed the above factors positively influence happiness among the personnel at work. Also, the study suggested that relationships, work quality and leadership highly affect the workplace happiness. Also, **Atkinson and Hall (2011)** examined the effect of one more determinant i.e., flexi working in the high-performance work system (HPWS) on the morale and behaviour of the workers at work. The researchers undergone a qualitative study based on the interviews of 43 directorates in a trust. The data collected from the interviews of the respondents were converted into transcripts and then analysed using NVivo software. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between flexible working time and employee's workplace happiness. The employees feel happy when the organization provides them the facility to choose flexible working hours. It also affects the performance of the employees positively. **Gavin et al. (2004)** concluded that there is a direct relationship between positive psychology and workplace happiness of employees. If organizations desire to have a healthy, happy and a productive workplace, they should focus on maintaining the positive psychology of employees which is free from stress and full of trust. **Thiruvankadam. T. et al. (2018)** the study was carried out with the aim to understand the level of happiness of employees in IT industry and to find out the determinants of employee's happiness. The study concluded with a remark that the constructs like work life balance, physical and mental well-being, relationship with managers has a significant influence on employee's happiness. **Singh et al. (2017)** examined the happiness of employees at work in manufacturing industry, India. The study concluded that relationship, quality of work life and leadership are the three main factors that affects the workplace happiness of employees.

Teachers are the most important members of our society. They give children purpose, set them up for success as citizens of our world, and inspire in them a drive to do well and succeed in life. Despite of dispositional traits, teachers have to face and cope with specific working conditions, which might result in either challenging or enhancing their happiness at work. Despite the number of researches, there exists a little empirical evidence for workplace happiness. More current research has examined the relationship of big five personality traits

with subjective happiness of employees, there is no emphasis in understanding the relationship between personality traits and happiness at workplace. Also, in various studies, the relationship of an important determinant of personality like agreeableness is not clear with happiness, which induces the need of research into this area.

Purpose: This study aims to examine the effect of big five personality types on workplace happiness among university teachers in Delhi/NCR.

Objectives:

1. To examine the effect of extraversion on workplace happiness of university teachers
2. To examine the effect of agreeableness on workplace happiness of university teachers
3. To examine the effect of conscientiousness on workplace happiness of university teachers
4. To examine the effect of openness on workplace happiness of university teachers
5. To examine the effect of neuroticism on workplace happiness of university teachers

Conceptual framework on effect of personality types on workplace happiness of university teachers

Materials and Methods

Variables: Workplace happiness is the dependent variable and extraversion, agreeableness, openness, conscientiousness and neuroticism are the independent variables.

The present study was descriptive in nature and the statistical population consisted of all the teachers working in UGC affiliated universities of Delhi/NCR. Since the population was unknown, therefore the sample size was determined through Daniel Soper Calculator.

Table 1

Anticipated effect of size	0.15
Desired statistical power level	0.8
Number of predictors	5
Probability level	0.05
Minimum required sample size	91

Daniel Soper Formula Calculator

As per the Daniel Soper Calculator, minimum sample required is 91, the questionnaire was sent to 272 teachers, wherein the responses received were 103. Cross tabulation was applied to determine the exact number of teacher's w.r.t. gender and designation

The data was selected using the Judgemental sampling wherein the respondents were university teachers from various disciplines in Delhi/NCR. The inclusion criteria were the nature of teacher's job. The teachers who are permanent faculty in university were included in the research.

As per data collection, a demographic questionnaire, the GSOEP big five inventory scale (15-items) and shorter version of workplace happiness scale (9- items) were used. The demographic questionnaire consisted of three questions on gender, designation and nature of job.

The GSOEP Big Five Inventory Scale (Shorter version by Elisabeth Hahn et al. 2012):

This instrument consisted of 15 questions with five-point Likert scale (1= strongly disagree, 2= Disagree a little, 3= Neutral, 4= Agree a little, 5= Agree Strongly). The GSOEP big five inventory traits questionnaire is one of the popular personality tests developed by Elisabeth Hahn et al. 2012. It is a shorter version of Big Five Inventory Scale comprising of 44-items developed by Oliver, 1999. Five dimensions of the scale are: extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness and neuroticism.

Happiness at Work Scale (Shorter version by Andres Salas- Vallina (2017). The instrument consisted of 9- items with five- point Likert scale (1= strongly disagree, 2= Disagree a little, 3= Neutral, 4= Agree a little, 5= Agree Strongly).

Statistical Analysis

To determine the normal distribution of data, the test was Kolmogorov- Smirnov applied. Further to determine the effect of personality types on workplace happiness, the regression analysis was used. In addition, T- test was applied to check the difference in the workplace happiness of university teacher's w.r.t. their gender and ANOVA was applied to check the difference in the workplace happiness w.r.t designation of the teachers.

All test were analysed through the SPSS statistics software V.21 at the significance level of 0.05 ($p < 0.001$).

Results

Table 2: Cross-tabulation

Variables	Groups	Number (%)
Gender	Male	24.27
	Female	80.34
Designation	Assistant Professor	44.6
	Associate Professor	32.03
	Professor	23.3

The participant's demographic characteristics

In the present study of the total 103 teachers, 25 (24.27%) are male teachers and 78 (80.34%) are female teachers and most of the teachers are having more than 3 years of teaching experience (82.52%). Majority of teachers are at the Assistant Professor level (44.6%).

Table 3: Regression

Model	R	R Square	Durbin-Watson	Sig.
1	.752 ^a	.566	1.828	.000

Table 3: Indicates the positive correlation between personality types and workplace happiness with coefficient .752. Also, the above results show the high strength of the model with sig. value of .000 which is <0.05.

Table 4:

Hypothesis	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Beta	Coefficient	Sig.	Hypothesis
1	Extraversion	Workplace Happiness	.359	.000	<0.05	Accepted
2	Agreeableness	Workplace Happiness	.285	.001	<0.05	Accepted
3	Openness	Workplace Happiness	.195	.007	<0.05	Accepted
4	Conscientiousness	Workplace Happiness	.073	.283	<0.05	Rejected
5	Neuroticism	Workplace Happiness	-.215	.005	<0.05	Accepted

The results demonstrated the positive effect of three of the personality traits on workplace happiness of university teachers namely extraversion (.000), suggesting if teachers are more extrovert, they would be happier at the workplace, agreeableness (.001) and openness (.007) which states teachers with high agreeableness and openness traits likely to be more happy at work. Conscientiousness (.283>.005) has no effect on workplace happiness of university teachers. The results also indicate the negative effect of neuroticism (.005) on workplace

happiness which means more the teachers having neuroticism personality, less likely they are happy at the workplace.

Table 5:

Variable	Sig. (Gender)	Sig. (Designation)	Decision
Workplace Happiness	.928>0.05	.605>0.05	p>0.05 indicating no difference in the workplace happiness of university teachers w.r.t gender and designation of university teachers.

Above results indicate the acceptance of null hypothesis, there is no significant difference in the workplace happiness of university teachers with respect to their gender and designation.

Discussion

The present study aimed to examine the effect of personality types on workplace happiness of university teachers in Delhi/NCR. The results of the present study showed that the personality types of teachers are average having the significant effect on their happiness at work. The results of the study were parallel with the results of (Momeni, 2010) wherein extraversion, agreeableness and openness positively affect the workplace happiness and neuroticism negatively effects the workplace happiness. Similar study done by (Goel, 2015) identified that there exists a positive correlation between personality traits and workplace happiness of women in Delhi/NCR. The present study has revealed the positive effect of three of the big five personality types on workplace happiness of university teachers. Conscientiousness as one of the important traits of big five personality has failed to show any effect on the workplace happiness of university teachers. Moreover, neuroticism has a negative effect on the workplace happiness, which means a teacher having higher neuroticism trait is less likely to be happy at workplace. Furthermore, there is no difference in the workplace happiness of university teacher's w.r.t gender and designation. Male and female teachers at assistant professor, associate professor and professor level are likely to have equivalent happiness level at work.

Limitations

The present study has several limitations. To mention a few, sample size was one of the major limitations of study. Further study should be undertaken on a larger sample size. The other limitation is that because of the individual differences of the research sample, the generalisability of the results may be affected.

Conclusion

The big five personality traits have a significant effect on workplace happiness of teachers. The findings of the present study can be used to create the awareness regarding the relationship between the personality types and workplace happiness of university teachers. Universities may consider the personality types as an intervention to foster the workplace happiness and may develop effective practices to foster the happiness among the teachers. It is suggested to

identify the type of personality that has the highest effect on workplace happiness to be further investigated in the form of comparative study.

Future Directions: The findings support the view that the dimensions of personality cause the propensity to be happy or not. The research has better explain the gender and designation level differences in personality types-to-workplace happiness, It has suggestively raise the consciousness in the academic direction of an individual teacher's personality types in everyday life, on the way to making universities a happier place of job and hence may help the academicians, administrators and researcher or policy makers by providing a model showing the relationships amongst the variables undertaken to frame the practices after considering these relationship

References

- Abdullah, A. G. K., Ling, Y. L., & Peng, C. S. (2016). An exploratory analysis of happiness at workplace from Malaysian teachers' perspective using performance-welfare model. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 6(6), 340-346.
- Abraham, S. (2015). Factors influencing workplace happiness among employees in software companies in Bangalore. *International Journal of Research in Applied Management Science & Technology II (I)*.
- Agbo, A. A., & Ngwu, C. N. (2017). Aversion to happiness and the experience of happiness: The moderating roles of personality. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 111, 227-231.
- Atkinson, C., Lucas, R., & Hall, L. (2011). Flexible working and happiness in the NHS. *Employee Relations*.
- Aziz Rashid, Mustaffa Sharif, Sanch A. Narina. (2014). Personality and Happiness among Academicians in Malaysia. *Procedia- Social Sciences*.
- Aziz, R., Mustaffa, S., Samah, N. A., & Yusof, R. (2014). Personality and happiness among academicians in Malaysia. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 116, 4209-4212.
- Bhattacharjee, D., & Bhattacharjee, M. (2010). Measuring happiness at work place. *ASBM Journal of Management*, 3(1/2), 112.
- Chaiprasit, K., & Santidhiraku, O. (2011). Happiness at work of employees in small and medium-sized enterprises, Thailand. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 25, 189-200.
- Chung, E., Mathew, V. N., & Subramaniam, G. (2019). In the Pursuit of Happiness: The Role of Personality. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9(11).
- Costa Jr, P. T., Terracciano, A., & McCrae, R. R. (2001). Gender differences in personality traits across cultures: robust and surprising findings. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 81(2), 322.
- DeNeve, K. M., & Cooper, H. (1998). The happy personality: A meta-analysis of 137 personality traits and subjective well-being. *Psychological bulletin*, 124(2), 197.
- Eysenck, H. J., & Eysenck, S. B. G. (1983). Recent advances in the cross-cultural study of personality. *Advances in personality assessment*, 2, 41-69.
- Field, L. K., & Buitendach, J. H. (2011). Happiness, work engagement and organisational commitment of support staff at a tertiary education institution in South Africa. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 37(1), 01-10.
- Gavin, J. H., & Mason, R. O. (2004). The Virtuous Organization: The Value of Happiness in the Workplace. *Organizational dynamics*, 33(4), 379-392.

Greenberg, J., & Baron, R. A. (1995). *Behavior in Organization*, Englewood Cliff, New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
Gronroos, C. (1990). Relationship approach to marketing in service contexts: the marketing and organizational behavior interface. *Journal of Business Research*, 20(1), 3-11.

Gyeltshen, C., & Beri, N. (2019). Comparison on the levels of work place happiness job satisfaction, organizational commitment and work motivation with respect to gender.

Kirkpatrick, B. L. (2015). *Personality and Happiness*.

Mohammed, A., & Dhabi, A. *Workplace Happiness and Positivity: Measurement, Causes and Consequences*.

Mohammed, A., & Dhabi, A. *Workplace Happiness and Positivity: Measurement, Causes and Consequences*.

Okwaraji, F. E., Nduanya, C. U., Okorie, A., & Okechukwu, H. E. (2017). Personality traits, happiness and life satisfaction, in a sample of Nigerian adolescents. *The Journal of Medical Research*, 3(6), 284-289.

Pishva, N., Ghalehban, M., Moradi, A., & Hoseini, L. (2011). Personality and happiness. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 30, 429-432.

Pishva, N., Ghalehban, M., Moradi, A., & Hoseini, L. (2011). Personality and happiness. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 30, 429-432.

Pishva, N., Ghalehban, M., Moradi, A., & Hoseini, L. (2011). Personality and happiness. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 30, 429-432.

Roessler, J., & Gloor, P. A. (2020). Measuring happiness increases happiness. *Journal of Computational Social Science*, 1-24.

Roy Rituparna, Konwar Juthika (2020). *Workplace Happiness: A Conceptual Framework*. *International Journal of Scientific & Technological Research*, 9

Sabatini, F. (2014). The relationship between happiness and health: evidence from Italy. *Social Science & Medicine*, 114, 178-187.

San Santoso, D., & Kulathunga, H. E. R. (2016). Examining happiness: Towards better understanding of performance improvement. *Procedia engineering*, 164, 354-361.

Sarang, S. D., Shitole, R. B., & Karnam, A. G. (2019). To investigate the association between sleep and happiness among nurses with different personality traits: A cross-sectional study. *The Indian Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 51(1), 3.

Sharma, N., & Gulati, J. K. (2015). Gender differences in happiness, self-esteem and personality traits in adolescents living in socio-economic hardship. *Adolescence*, 54(78), 75.

Sheldon, K. M., & Elliot, A. J. (1999). Goal striving, need satisfaction, and longitudinal well-being: the self-concordance model. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 76(3), 482.

Sohail, M., & Rehman, C. A. (2015). Stress and health at the workplace-a review of the literature. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 6(3), 94.

Wesarat, P. O., Sharif, M. Y., & Abdul Majid, A. H. (2014). A conceptual framework of happiness at the workplace. *Asian Social Science*, 11(2), 78-88.

Woo, H., & Ahn, H. J. (2015). Big five personality and different meanings of happiness of consumers. *Economics & Sociology*, 8(3), 145.

Ziapour, A., Khatony, A., Jafari, F., & Kianipour, N. (2018). Correlation of Personality Traits with Happiness among University Students. *Journal of Clinical & Diagnostic Research*, 12(4).